

Light induced electron transfer reactions : kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of hexacyanoferrate(II) by peroxodisulphate induced by irradiation of visible light in presence of tris(2,2'-bipyridine)ruthenium(II) ion photocatalyst in aqueous solutions^ψ

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The oxidation reaction of hexacyanoferrate(II) by peroxodisulphate ($S_2O_8^{2-}$) is accelerated by irradiation with visible light in aqueous acid solutions containing tris(2,2'-bipyridine)ruthenium(II) ion ($Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}$), the latter acts as a photocatalyst. The mechanism of the reaction consists of a chain reaction initiated by the quenching reaction of the photo excited ruthenium(II) complex ion ($^{\ominus}Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}$), with $S_2O_8^{2-}$. The rate law is expressed by the equation

$$-\frac{1}{2} \frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = \frac{k_q I_a \phi [S_2O_8^{2-}]}{k_o + k_q [S_2O_8^{2-}]}$$

k_q is the bimolecular quenching rate constant and has been determined kinetically. Other terms have their usual meaning.

The chemistry of the excited electronic states of diimine substituted d^6 metal complexes has been a subject matter of extensive studies more particularly in view of applications in a large number of areas. However, the studies on $[Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}]$ complex ion are larger in number than the other substituted derivatives. In fact, a large number of attractive features¹⁻⁵ such as the chemical stability of the ground state, the reactivity of the excited state, luminescence emission and redox properties have made these compounds to be the subject matter of extensive exploitation for solar energy conversion.

$[Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}]$ photoluminescence⁶⁻⁸ provides information not only about the quencher molecules but also about the microenvironment around the probe⁹. Since oxygen is considered to be an effective quencher for ruthenium complexes^{10,11}, the concentration of oxygen can be determined in such quenching studies as well.

Peroxodisulphate ion is one of the most useful oxidative quenchers¹²⁻¹⁴ of the excited $[^{\ominus}Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}]$. The decomposition of the peroxodisulphate ion upon photo-reduction into two ions minimizes the back electron transfer reaction. Since SO_4^{2-} – a reduced form of peroxodisulphate ion is practically inert and is not considered to be a pollutant, peroxodisulphate ion is an ideal candidate for the tech-

nological applications in the process of photography to oxidize silver or in the processes of certain dye formations.

Peroxodisulphate ion despite possessing high redox potential thermally reacts slowly. Nevertheless the metal ions such as Ag^I or Cu^{II} are known to catalyze these reactions. Since hexacyanoferrate(II) is also considered to be photosensitive, probing the reaction mechanism of peroxodisulphate – $Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$ reaction in the presence of photocatalyst can provide better insight of the reaction events. Also a comparative pattern of reactivity in the presence of photocatalyst in visible light induced reactions and the metal ion catalyzed thermal reactions can be delineated to gain more chemistry of these catalysts which operate in different environment of the reaction. These were certain observations that prompted us to undertake the kinetic study of the title reaction.

Experimental

Materials :

Peroxodisulphate (E. Merck) was employed as supplied and its aqueous solution was prepared by dissolving its potassium salt in desired volume. The solution was standardized iodometrically in the presence of $(Cu^{II}-Fe^{III})$ catalyst. Since the solution of persulphate is not much stable, a

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

fresh solutions of this oxidant were used as and when required. Tris(2,2'-bipyridyl)ruthenium(II) was a chloride salt (Aldrich) and was used as supplied. Its solution in water is quite stable provided it is kept in bottles painted black from the outside at refrigerated temperature (-5°) in dark.

All other chemicals were either of AnalaR or guaranteed reagent grade. Doubly distilled water was employed throughout the study, the second distillation was from alkaline permanganate solution in an all glass apparatus.

Kinetic procedure :

The photosensitized reactions were allowed to occur in the colourless glass vessels of dimensions as mentioned elsewhere. Tungsten filament lamp was the source of radiations. The temperature of the reaction was kept at less than -40° during irradiation of the reaction mixture. All the reaction ingredients except peroxydisulphate were taken in these glass vessels and the nitrogen gas free of oxygen was flushed through these mixtures at least for 15 min prior to initiating the reaction. The requisite amount of peroxydisulphate was then injected into the reaction mixture without interrupting flushing of nitrogen, the time of initiation was recorded when half of the solution of peroxydisulphate was released. The serum rubber caps were employed to check the contact of oxygen of the environment with the contents of the reaction mixture. The absence of oxygen was tested time and again in the reaction vessel qualitatively. Since such tests were always negative, this confirmed the presence of peroxydisulphate as the only quencher in the reaction mixture.

An aliquot (5 or 10 cm³) of the reaction mixture was taken out without stopping irradiation by employing hypodermic syringes and then assayed for the built-up of hexacyanoferrate(III) periodically spectrophotometrically at 418 nm ($\epsilon \sim 1020 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Initial rates were computed¹⁵ by employing plane mirror method. Hexacyanoferrate(II) was transparent at this wavelength¹⁶. However, rates in triplicate were reproducible to within $\pm 6\%$.

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined under experimental conditions with an excess of peroxydisulphate over hexacyanoferrate(II) and was found to correspond to the reaction as represented by eq. (1),

The product hexacyanoferrate(III) was determined in a kinetic run at infinite time that corresponded to the initial concentration of hexacyanoferrate(II) to within $\pm 5\%$. None-

theless, similar stoichiometry has earlier been reported¹⁷ in $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} - \text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ reaction.

Results

Effect of concentration of reactants :

Initial rates (k_i) were calculated and these were found to be independent of the initial concentrations of hexacyanoferrate(II) over the concentration range ($5.0 \times 10^{-4} - 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$) mol dm⁻³, however, rates exhibit peroxydisulphate dependence in the concentration range ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} - 6.0 \times 10^{-3}$) mol dm⁻³ (Fig. 1) giving an empiri-

Fig. 1. Variation of peroxydisulphate. $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Light = 100 W, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 418 \text{ nm}$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] = (\odot) 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$; $(\bullet) 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ and $(\Delta) 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

cal relationship between the concentration of peroxydisulphate and initial rate (k_i) represented by eq. (2),

$$(k_i)^{-1} = A + B[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where A and B are empirical constants. Since the ionic strength of the reaction mixtures was not kept constant, A and B parameters can be evaluated only for a single run or for the variation of peroxydisulphate at fixed concentration of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ at a fixed ionic strength. Thus a plot of $(k_i)^{-1}$ versus $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]^{-1}$ was made from eq. (2) that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 2) A and B were evaluated from the intercept and slope respectively.

Effect of temperature :

The temperature in the range $25-40^{\circ}$ does not exhibit

Fig. 2. A plot of $(k_i)^{-1}$ versus $[S_2O_8^{2-}]^{-1}$. $[Ru^{II}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-7}$ mol dm^{-3} , Light = 100 W, $\lambda_{max} = 418$ nm, $[Fe(CN)_6^{4-}] = (\odot) 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$; $(\bullet) 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ and $(\Delta) 3.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} .

any effect on the rate of the reaction. Since no thermal reaction was allowed, no effect of the temperature in the above range was observed. Quenching rates are rather insensitive to temperature in the range 8–45°. Over the same temperature variation, the lifetime of $[^{\otimes}Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}]$ decreases by ~35% due to thermal equilibration of the luminescent metal-to-ligand charge transfer state to a set of energetically higher metal non-bonding states which are known to undergo photosubstitution or rapid radiationless decay ($k \sim 10^{-13}$ s) to the ground state. The life-time of the photo excited ion-pair $[^{\otimes}Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}, S_2O_8^{2-}]$ is independent of temperature. This further suggests that ion-pairing does not perturb the rate of radiationless decay through these states^{18–20}.

Effect of incident light :

It is worth mentioning that the decomposition of peroxodisulphate in the dark is not appreciable under the experimental conditions of the kinetics of title reaction. However, there is a perfect proportionality between the initial rate and the number of lamps employed for irradiation of the reaction mixtures (Fig. 3).

Effect of hydrogen ion concentration :

The effect of hydrogen ion on the rate was studied in the pH range 2.8–7.15, however, initial rate is independent of hydrogen ion concentration. Similar pH effect has also been reported elsewhere. The observed enhancement of the rate in case of oxidation of arsenic(III) by peroxodisulphate

Fig. 3. Variation of incident light. $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Fe(CN)_6^{4-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Ru^{II}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-7}$ mol dm^{-3} , $\lambda_{max} = 418$ nm.

in the pH range >8 and in the presence of photocatalyst is reportedly accounted for the higher reactivity of the deprotonated species of arsenic acid²¹. This is obviously not the case in the $Fe(CN)_6^{4-} - S_2O_8^{2-}$ reaction under almost identical experimental conditions.

Effect of concentration of $[Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}]$:

The effect of the $[Ru(bipy)_3^{2+}]$ was studied in the concentration range $(1.0 \times 10^{-7} - 1.0 \times 10^{-6})$ mol dm^{-3} keeping fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients with constant irradiation. Initial rate (k_i) was plotted against the concentrations of the photocatalyst, a straight line with minor path was also observed. Trace metal ion catalysis in irradiated solution does not have any role to play. Thus in all probability it appears to be an outcome due to experimental uncertainty. Nevertheless, the direct proportionality of the light intensity and initial rate eliminate any such possibility.

Effect of radical scavengers :

Acrylic acid or acrylonitrile is known to be an efficient scavengers of $SO_4^{\bullet-}$ radical ions. The addition of either of these compounds in the reaction mixture produced a white sediment considered to be a polymer. Such an observation ascribes to the fact that the light induced reaction occurs through the intervention of the radical species. This has also been observed²² in other cases.

Scheme 1

Mechanism of the reaction :

These observations as stated above can be accounted for the mechanism as envisaged below :

$[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{3+}]$ is reportedly unstable in aqueous solution of $\text{pH} > 4$. Oxidative degradation of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{3+}]$ to the bipyridine ligand was found in the presence of solid catalysts such as RuO_2 or IrO_2 , the latter are known to accelerate the rate of oxidation¹⁹ of water by $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{3+}]$. The rate of oxidation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ by $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{3+}]$ is much faster than the oxidation of water, therefore, steady state concentration of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{3+}]$ is very small under experimental conditions. Probably this appears to be the sole reason that the decomposition of ruthenium(II) complex was not observed.

Applying steady-state treatment to the concentrations of intermediates such as $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$, $[^{\circ}\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{3+}]$, the rate law (9) or (10) is obtained.

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = \frac{k_q I_a \phi [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{k_0 + k_q [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{or } (k_i)^{-1} = \frac{1}{I_a \phi} + \frac{k_0}{k_q I_a \phi} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]^{-1} \quad (10)$$

where ϕ is efficiency of formation of the excited species. I_a is the intensity of light absorbed by $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ and $I_a \phi$ is the rate of formation of the excited species. The rate eq. (10) is similar to that of the empirical rate law (2). Therefore, A corresponds to $(I_a \phi)^{-1}$ and B to $(k_0/k_q I_a \phi)$. The plot of $(k_i)^{-1}$ versus $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]^{-1}$ yielded a straight line from which A and B were calculated. The ratio of A and B yielded k_q to be $(3.37 \times 10^8) \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ which is in quite good agreement of the value reported earlier²¹ (5.33×10^8 and $8.0 \times 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ without specifying ionic strength on the basis of Stern-Volmer plots in the measurements of quenching luminescence). Since A/B ratio is independent of the temperature, k_q is also not affected by the temperature.

Thus the mechanistic events of this reaction in the presence of photocatalyst can be accounted for the Scheme 1.

When eq. (10) holds, the concentration of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ ion remains constant during the reaction and acts as a photocatalyst.

Since k_q was not determined at different but fixed ionic strength, it is difficult to quantify the effect of ionic strength on the quenching rate constant. However, a qualitative picture of this effect emerges out of the reactive intermediate species, its charge and interaction. If we consider the following steps (12)–(14), a reasonably good account of the effect of ionic strength can be given similar to conclusions reported by Kimura *et al.*¹⁴.

Applying steady state treatment to the concentrations of intermediate species, eq. (15) is obtained.

$$k_q = k_1 k_3 k_5 / (k_2 + k_3) (k_4 + k_5) - k_3 k_4 \quad (15)$$

when $k_2 \gg k_3$ and $k_4 \gg k_5$, $k_3 k_4$ term is negligible, the eq. (15) is reduced to eq. (16),

$$\begin{aligned} k_q &= k_1 k_3 k_5 / k_2 k_4 \\ \text{or } k_1 / k_2 \cdot k_3 / k_1 \cdot k_5 & \\ \text{or } k_q &= K_1 K_2 k_5 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

If we consider the steps (12), (13) and (14) respectively, K_2 is the equilibrium constant for the ion pair in the solvent cage and as such it should not be affected by ionic strength. Thus the ionic strength effect on the rate can be attributed to K_1 and k_5 . Further, K_1 and k_5 ascribe to the ion pair association and ion dissociation steps respectively, such a counter-balancing effect is not expected to bring a significant ionic strength effect on the quenching rate constant and the real ionic strength effect on k_q cannot be ascertained. Moreover, k_q would not be much affected by ionic strength despite the charge products of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$.

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